

Annual Report

2018

SND

Swedish National Data Service

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Foreword

2018 has been a year of crucial importance for SND. It is the first year in the new consortium, where SND is governed by seven large Swedish universities with a very strong outreach to most research disciplines. The consortium is further described on the coming pages. This year has also been the first year with a network of universities that form a collaboration in discussing principles of research data management within Open Science. In total 29 universities and a couple of other research-active authorities have signed a letter of intent, expressing a local commitment and an obligation to build a local support unit to help the researchers working with Open Data in their respective organisation. The SND collaboration, with a rather unique bottom-up perspective based on the universities and their researchers, gives us a strong voice in the Swedish development of Open Science and Open Data. Our network and network meetings are further described on later pages.

In late 2018, the Annual Assembly approved a strategic plan* for 2018–2022, highlighting a number of important tasks for building a long-term infrastructure that will provide the Open Data services needed in order for the Swedish

research community to be able to work with Open Science and to be competitive when applying for research grants and publishing scientific papers.

A crucial part of the strategic plan is metadata profiles and e-tools. During the year, in cooperation with Swedish universities and in international collaborations such as CESSDA and CLARIN (see descriptions on the following pages), we have worked intensively to fine-tune and implement metadata profiles for a number of research disciplines, with an objective to cover all research disciplines over the coming five year period. The profiles are now being implemented in a makeover of the e-tools for metadata management that SND offers.

Last but not least, I want to thank all of you who have contributed to this positive development for SND. I believe that together we will be able to finalize a number of our newly started initiatives during 2019 and begin the next phase of a distributed Open Data work involving the Swedish universities.

*Max Petzold,
Director of SND*

*The strategic plan can be found on SND's website.

The SND Consortium

In 2016, a consortium of seven of the largest universities in Sweden was formed to govern SND. In March 2017 the Swedish National Research Council granted the consortium funding for the period 2018–2022, and the reconstruction of SND to function as a consortium with a federated system for handling and storing research data within Open Science was initiated. The change is directed by the strategic plan for 2018–2022. As of January 2018, the SND consortium, governed by University of Gothenburg, Karolinska Institutet, Lund University, Stockholm University, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Umeå University, and Uppsala University, is up and running. SND is controlled by an annual assembly and a steering committee which meets about four times a year. What is most valuable for researchers is that they through the consortium will get more local support in managing their data in accordance with the FAIR principles*. It is also important for the universities that our federated data storage solutions enable the researchers to follow Swedish law for all types of data, including sensitive personal data. We are implementing FAIR based on the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”.

The size of SND should remain small, but the total number of people involved in the work with Open Data will increase. We are building a distributed knowledge hub where the different consortium universities are allocating expertise, so called “Domain Specialists”, based on the needs of the collaboration. Most of these domain specialists are active researchers who work part time for SND. The SND office provides experts in Open Data and the domain specialists bring in research domain expertise that enables us to develop metadata standards that are useful for each research domain, e-tools that provide support to the researchers in managing their data, and to initiate Open Data activities in their research domains etc. The domain specialists will change over time to fit SND’s current needs. On average, each consortium university will allocate one full-time position as a domain specialist, divided on several researchers and other specialists such as data safety managers, lawyers etc.

*Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable

Network and Consortium Events

The SND Consortium is connected to a wider network of institutions, which is central to the operations and mission of SND. By the end of 2018, the SND Network consisted of 30 members in total. Among these were 29 Swedish universities and one research-active authority, as listed below. The network members are all in different stages of establishing a local unit or function for managing research data, a Data Access Unit (DAU).

Network Meetings

During 2018 SND organised four network meetings, each with a different theme. Among the participants were mainly representatives from the 30 network members, but the meetings were open to other interested parties as well. Every network meeting gathered 70 to 80 participants.

5 March, Research Data – From DAU to SND

The first network meeting of 2018 was located at Stockholm University and focused on the research data workflow. The aim was to discuss how to move forward in constructing SND's future distribution model, consisting of local data management units (DAUs). At the meeting, representatives from Stockholm University and the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences gave an account of their experiences from working with research data.

Members of the SND Network

Consortium members in bold text.

1. Blekinge Institute of Technology
2. Chalmers University of Technology
3. Dalarna University
4. Halmstad University
5. Jönköping University
6. Karlstad University
- 7. Karolinska Institutet**
8. Kristianstad University Sweden
9. KTH Royal Institute of Technology
10. Linköping University
11. Linnaeus University
12. Luleå University of Technology
- 13. Lund University**
14. Malmö University
15. Mid Sweden University
16. Mälardalen University
17. Stockholm School of Economics
- 18. Stockholm University**
19. Swedish Defence University
20. Swedish Polar Research Secretariat
- 21. Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences**
22. Södertörn University
- 23. Umeå University**
24. University of Borås
- 25. University of Gothenburg**
26. University of Gävle
27. University of Skövde
28. University West
- 29. Uppsala University**
30. Örebro University

Margareta Åkesson (HV), Johan Fihn Marberg (SND), Hanna Lindroos and Mikaela Asplund (SLU) at the network meeting on 5 March.

Their experiences then served as practical examples from which to start a general discussion among the participants.

On other topics, Karl Gertow and Magnus Ericsson spoke on the role of the Swedish Research Council (VR) in coordinating the promotion of open access to research data at a national level. Leif Johansson from Sunet highlighted the need for a national platform for storage, and presented the project to develop a solution whereby Sunet sells data storage space to higher education institutions, infrastructures, and larger research groups.

Participants also received a status update on SND's ongoing projects "My SND" and "The DAU Handbook", which are tools that will facilitate the work on managing research data in the Data Access Units.

11 June, To Establish and Work in a DAU - Policies, Demands and Needs

SND's second network meeting in Gothenburg addressed the question of how higher education

institutions can organise their efforts to produce and disseminate research data that follow the FAIR principles.

The first topic was how best to implement policies and guidelines for managing research data. Sabina Anderberg, Business Developer at Stockholm University Library, highlighted the advantages of a well-established and well-formulated research data policy. Peter Linde, Librarian at Blekinge Institute of Technology (BTH), then went on to describe BTH's ongoing effort to develop a research data policy and create an organisation for managing research data.

Jeremy Azzopardi, Data Manager at SND, presented the first version of SND's Metadata and Research Data Requirements Description, which aims to be a useful resource for university institutions in their work with research data. The day concluded with a panel discussion on educational materials on data management for researchers.

8 October, Outward, Inward and Forward

In the third network meeting in Gothenburg, international cooperation was the main focus. Some of the international organisations and initiatives working to develop and promote an open research data landscape were highlighted.

Ron Dekker, Director of CESSDA (Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives), gave an opening presentation about the importance of international research data infrastructures. SND's Senior Advisor Iris Alfredsson then went on to outline the CESSDA-related work being carried out in Sweden, followed by short presentations of other

international research data initiatives and collaborations such as RDA (Research Data Alliance), CLARIN (Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure), Core Trust Seal, DataCite, and DDI (Data Documentation Initiative).

The participants were also given a progress update on the Sunet project for a shared national storage solution for research data, and Magnus Eriksson from the Swedish Research Council spoke about the assessment criteria for FAIR data. Finally, SND's Jeremy Azzopardi gave a preview of SND's DAU Handbook.

In connection to the meeting, SND invited the archivists within the network to a separate meeting on 9 October, together with Sofia Särndqvist from the National Archive and representatives from SND. This meeting was a first step towards a deeper collaboration on issues concerning research data archiving.

4 December, To Establish a DAU – Challenges, Solutions and Inspiration

The Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU) hosted the fourth and final network meeting of the year, which focused on the experiences gained by the universities during their DAU establishment processes. In the course of the day, six presentations were held by representatives from the Swedish University of Agricultural Studies, Karolinska Institutet, University of Gothenburg, Halmstad University, Örebro University, and Karlstad University. Hanna Lindroos from SLU also presented a short survey carried out ahead of the meeting, showing the diversity in how the network's DAUs are composed.

During the DAU presentations, similarities soon emerged. Common themes highlighted by the participants were the need for communication efforts, further training in data management, and organisational resources like competency, time, and funding.

SND's Elisabeth Strandhagen gave a status update on the ongoing work with adapting SND's research data description form to various research disciplines, the DAU Handbook, and the rollout of SND's new graphic profile. Director Max Petzold briefly summarised national news in the research data field, and Olof Olsson and Johan Fihn Marberg introduced SND's coming pilot project, which will test a work process where SND and a group of researchers from pilot universities make research data accessible and arrange local storage solutions with the universities.

Exercise to gauge progress towards the creation of local data management units (DAUs) at the network meeting on 11 June.

Workshop for Consortium Members

The day after the December network meeting, SND arranged a workshop hosted by Karolinska Institutet. The workshop, called *“Building the Capabilities for a Professional RDM Support Service”*, was aimed at consortia members, especially those working as domain specialists or in some way involved in DAU-specific work.

Lead by Angus Whyte and Shanmugasundaram Venkataraman from the Digital Curation Centre (DCC) in Edinburgh, the objective of the workshop was to give a background to capability modelling in research data management and to gain awareness of new developments in capability modelling for services that support the stewardship of open research and data science.

Capability modelling can be used to provide a comprehensive image of the service development within an organisation. It is also a means to reflect on the level of ambition and driving forces for change and improvement in the service development process. The workshop participants were guided on how to identify common elements of a research data management service and information sources for service development. Taking examples from their own organisations, the participants were also invited to reflect on the stakeholders that influence the development of services and policies.

Collaboration within the Network

Appointed Contact Persons

During 2018, SND has given every member of the network a contact person in the SND office. Establishing this form of relationship will promote dialogue and knowledge exchange between the network and the SND office, and strengthen the ties between the network and SND.

Collaborative Projects

The ongoing work in SND’s projects is carried out by a number of working groups. The majority of these groups are based in the SND office, but some are collaborations that include members of the consortium and network. Among the collaborative groups are the DAU Handbook Group and the Communications Group.

The DAU Handbook Group

The “handbook” is the guidelines that will describe how SND wants the work with research data to be carried out in the universities and their DAUs. The publication of metadata and data will e.g. include a quality control, and the handbook will provide help in how to assure that data and metadata handed in by researchers fulfil SND’s quality requirements.

Communications Group

One of the responsibilities of the Communications Group is to identify what information is needed to establish the roles of domain specialist and DAU. The group will specify which communication channels and tools to use when exchanging experiences and knowledge within SND, as well as between SND and the DAUs.

SND's network consists of the Swedish universities that have agreed to create local units for managing research data (Data Access Units or DAUs). In 2018, the network had 30 members from all over Sweden.

Successful Collaboration with the University of Borås

In spring 2018, the University of Borås and the Swedish National Data Service jointly offered a professional-development course to staff in the local data access support functions. The 120 hour distance course, *Forskningsdata: tillgänglighet, hantering, samverkan* ("Research Data: Accessibility, Management, Collaboration"), builds on the BAS initiative from 2016 and '17 and uses blended learning with four physical meetings. The course has three main objectives:

- 1) to develop participants' data management skills and ability to support researchers in managing, documenting, and making data FAIR
- 2) to increase participants' understanding of the institutional conditions for providing access to research data
- 3) to strengthen the national network through interpersonal connections and collegial ties.

In order to promote collaboration between participants and to take advantage of their various types and levels of expertise and experience, Active Learning Classroom (ALC) methodology is used during the physical meetings. Participants work actively in groups with instructor-facilitated tasks. The ALC work is combined with significant use of collaborative work between meetings.

Participants' data management skills were developed through case-focused ALC exercises. The combination of studying material in advance and having to put the information to use in group work proved to be an efficient way of identifying how the new information could be applied to actual situations. Institutional conditions necessary for data access were addressed through concrete tasks and discussions of the participants' own situations and challenges.

A clear outcome of the course was a strengthening of the SND network. Participants gained a sense of collegiality by working in different constellations during various tasks. The social activities intentionally included in the course allowed classroom discussions to flow into more informal spaces. Participants got to know each other and the teachers from SND and the University of Borås, thus lowering the threshold for future collaborations and mutual assistance within the network.

The 2018 course had twenty-one participants from twelve universities in the SND network. It will run again during spring 2019.

Overview of an Active Learning Classroom at the University of Borås.
Photo by Helena Francke.

International Cooperation

During 2018, SND has continued its international cooperation, mainly by participating in the work within ESFRI landmarks in the Social & Cultural Innovation domain¹, such as the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA)² and the Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure (CLARIN)³.

CESSDA

Since its establishment in 1976, CESSDA has served as an informal umbrella organisation for European national social science data archives. CESSDA has been on the ESFRI Roadmap since 2006. It became a legal institution (CESSDA AS) in 2013 and then an ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium) in 2017. The mission of CESSDA is to provide a full-scale sustainable research infrastructure enabling the research community to conduct high-quality research in the social sciences contributing to the production of effective solutions to the major challenges facing society today and to facilitate teaching and learning in the social sciences.

At the end of 2018 the CESSDA consortium was composed of sixteen member countries and one observer. Each member country has a designated Service Provider (SP) that meets specific demands and requirements specified in the CESSDA Statutes. SND is the appointed Swedish SP. The CESSDA Strategy builds on four pillars: trust, training, technology, and tools & services. For each of these pillars there are CESSDA working groups and within these groups, there are CESSDA projects and regular meetings for alignment.

The yearly CESSDA Work Plan includes a number of tasks to be carried out in partnership by the SPs. In 2018, SND continued its participation in CESSDA Metadata Management phase 2 and Controlled Vocabularies (CV) Manager, two tasks that started within the Work Plan 2017⁴. Furthermore, SND was involved in eight tasks included in the Work Plan 2018⁵:

- CESSDA Widening Activities 2018
- DataverseEU 2018
- Enhanced Data Management Training
- European Question Bank 2018
- Implementing the CESSDA Persistent Identifier Policy
- Technical Framework 2018
- Trust 2018
- Vocabulary Services Multilingual Content Management

¹<http://roadmap2018.esfri.eu/projects-and-landmarks/browse-the-catalogue/?domain=Social+%26+Cultural+Innovation>

²<https://www.cessda.eu/>

³<https://www.clarin.eu/>

⁴<https://www.cessda.eu/About/Projects/Work-Plans/Work-Plan-2017>

⁵<https://www.cessda.eu/About/Projects/Work-Plans/Work-Plan-2018>

CLARIN

CLARIN makes digital language resources available to scholars, researchers, students, and citizen-scientists from all disciplines, especially in the humanities and social sciences, through single sign-on access. CLARIN is a distributed network, consisting of the CLARIN ERIC, national consortia, centres of expertise of various types, and online services. CLARIN was established as an ERIC in 2012 and Sweden joined the CLARIN ERIC during 2014. SND is part of the Swe-Clarín consortium.

During 2018, SND's Swe-Clarín team has spent significant effort in designing a metadata profile for describing language resources, and a resource catalogue to display Swe-Clarín resources for potential users. The team has also provided assistance to the new design of the Swe-Clarín website. Internationally, team members have continued their involvement with the CLARIN User Involvement Group, which works to find ways to reach humanities and social science researchers and explain how they can make use of CLARIN tools and resources in their research.

Other International Cooperations

During 2018, SND participated in several meetings in preparation for submitting a Swedish application for membership in the Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH)⁶.

The Swedish membership in the Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research (ICPSR)⁷ is administered by SND. SND awards scholarships for participating in the ICPSR's Summer Program in Quantitative Methods of Social Research⁸, and in 2018 eight scholarships were awarded.

The participation in international organisations within the areas of metadata standards and persistent identifiers has continued during 2018 through the memberships in the DDI (Data Documentation Initiative) Alliance⁹ and DataCite¹⁰. SND staff is also represented in the CoreTrust-Seal¹¹ Assembly of Reviewers. Other international memberships are in the International Federation of Data Organisations (IFDO)¹² and the World Data System (WDS)¹³.

Two organisations where SND staff are involved are the Research Data Alliance (RDA)¹⁴ and the International Association for Social Science Information Services & Technology (IASSIST)¹⁵. During 2018 SND was represented at the RDA Eleventh Plenary Meeting in Berlin, and at the Nordic RDA meeting in Helsinki. At the Nordic meeting the recently established network of national RDA nodes in Europe was discussed. At the time of the meeting, Finland had established a RDA node and Denmark had sent in an application to set up a node. Norway and Sweden declared an interest in applying in the call starting in January 2019.

⁶<https://www.dariah.eu/>

⁷<https://www.icpsr.umich.edu/>

⁸<https://www.icpsr.umich.edu/icpsrweb/sumprog/>

⁹<http://www.ddialliance.org/>

¹⁰<https://datacite.org/>

¹¹<https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

¹²<http://ifdo.org/>

¹³<https://www.icsu-wds.org/>

¹⁴<https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

¹⁵<https://iassistdata.org/>

Hosting IASSIST 2020

In 2018 SND prepared a proposal for hosting the 2020 IASSIST Conference. The proposal was submitted in the beginning of 2019.

Upcoming Projects

During 2018, SND participated in writing applications for three infrastructure projects within the European Union H2020 Programme. ARIADNE-plus is the extension of the ARIADNE project (2013–2017), SSHOC (Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud) is a cluster project to create a European open cloud ecosystem for social sciences and humanities, and EOSC-Nordic is a project aiming to facilitate the coordination of EOSC relevant initiatives within the Nordic and Baltic countries. SND also participated in the COST Action application Saving European Archeology from the Digital Dark Age, SEADDA. All projects were funded and will start in 2019.

Samuel Abera, Marleen Poot and Yabebal Ayalew during SND's two-week data management training.

Collaboration with EfD and Ethiopia

In September 2018 SND hosted a data management and researcher support training programme with participants from the Environment and Climate Research Center in Addis Abeba, Ethiopia. The initiative is part of the SND collaboration with the Environment for Development Initiative (EfD) and is aiming to build an EfD data curation center in Addis Abeba.

Some of the international organisations that SND were involved in during 2018.

Dissemination Statistics

Finding Data through SND

SND has a total of 1,934 searchable studies from a variety of research areas.

Downloaded Material

Many studies in SND's catalogue are available to download directly. The total number of downloads from the SND website in 2018 was 4,032. The most downloaded study was Memorialisation in Norrtälje, Mariehamn and Pargas 1881–1939 (SND 0918) with 885 downloads.

Orders

Material which is not available for download directly from the SND website is available by order. The following statistics refer solely to this material. In 2018, SND received a total of 523 orders. A total of 1,659 datasets were supplied during the year.

YEAR	NUMBER OF ORDERS
2014	472
2015	459
2016	521
2017	542
2018	523

Series in Demand

Studies that form part of a series are among the most popular. The two series with by far the greatest number of orders in 2018 were the National Society Opinion Media (SOM) surveys and the Swedish National Election Studies. The Swedish part of the ISSP and the SVT Exit Poll Surveys were also popular in 2018.

SND Online Analysis

A number of datasets such as those in the series International Social Survey Programme (ISSP), European Social Survey (ESS) and Institutional Trust can also be accessed through SND Online Analysis. There were 58 applications for SND Online Analysis accounts in 2018. Information about the number of downloads from Online Analysis is not currently available.

ECDS (Environment Climate Data Sweden)

Migration of ECDS services to SND will be completed in 2019. Researchers already deposit new data through SND's portal using the Earth and Environmental sciences research data profile, and the ECDS portal is closed for new submissions. During 2018, around 40 studies were transferred from ECDS to SND's catalogue, and the remaining data will be transferred early 2019. The ECDS portal will be formally withdrawn in 2019, and all ecds.se dataset URLs will be redirected to either SND catalogue entries or other relevant information.

SERIES IN DEMAND

SERIES	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
National SOM (Society Opinion Media)	389	308	478	537	406
Swedish National Election Studies – Parliamentary Elections	355	265	359	456	400
International Social Survey Programme (ISSP)*	81	95	94	117	131
SVT Exit Poll Surveys	157	107	40	32	49
Western SOM	31	95	86	86	36
Road Safety Survey	7	7	4	36	35
Swedish Electoral Data	133	28	20	32	29
Welfare State Surveys	35	37	40	25	26
Media Barometer	5	19	15	14	25
European Social Survey*	16	16	16	38	17
Institutional Trust*	14	0	2	0	15
SOM – Special Studies	5	1	2	10	15
Swedish National Election Studies – European Parliament Elections	27	4	21	25	14
SOM-undersökningarna i Skåne	6	14	14	8	10
Swedish National Election Studies – Referendums	8	2	0	16	7
Total	1 269	998	1 191	1 432	1 215

**Also available via SND Online Analysis*

The table only includes the 15 most demanded series in 2018.

DOWNLOADS AND DATASETS SUPPLIED

Downloads from SND's catalogue and datasets disseminated.

Downloads from Environment Climate Data Sweden (ECDS) are not included for 2017 or 2018 for technical reasons.

**Comprehensive statistics on the number of downloads are not available for 2014 for technical reasons, so the actual figure may be higher.*

Economy

Notes

1. Network services were not included in the budget

2. Internal co-financing of previous CESSDA projects

3. Final payments for EU-projects finalising in 2017

4. ICPSR membership and scholarships for transfer

5. Co-financing from Gothenburg university for EU-projects 2017

6. Accruals for projects finalising in 2019

7. Lower staffing costs due to leave of absence

8. Increased cost for premises due to use of offices from other department

9. Funds returned to coordinator due to overpayment

10. Further replacements of technical equipment than planned

11. Lower consulting costs for IT and economist

12. Costs for IT support were not included in the budget

13. Higher costs for DoSp due to more conferences and travels

*DoSp - Domain Specialist

The ending balance shows an accumulated capital of 6 702 which will be used for activities within the SND Network over a four-year period.

	Notes	Results	Budget
REVENUES			
Swedish Research Council, Core activities		13 000	13 000
Government Grants		7 000	7 000
Swedish Research Council, CESSDA activities		1 000	1 000
Other Income - SND Network Services	1.	1 575	0
Other Income - CESSDA Tasks		1 047	1 167
Internal Co-financing SND	2.	807	0
EU-projects (ARIADNE+CESSDA SaW)	3.	582	0
Swedish Research Council, ICPSR	4.	350	0
Internal Co-financing GU	5.	248	0
Subsidised salaries		93	0
Other income		6	0
Accruals	6.	-829	1 206
Other Income - Speech Resource Bank		0	839
Total revenues		24 879	24 212
EXPENSES			
Fixed expenses			
Staff	7.	-16 959	-18 088
Premises	8.	-1 134	-1 051
Swedish Research Council, ESFRI (Swe-CLARIN)	9.	-286	0
Other Operating Costs		-159	-169
IT Infrastructure	10.	-181	-75
IT Licenses		-159	-159
Membership fees		-167	-165
Consulting fees	11.	-301	-555
University IT fee incl. support	12.	-442	-371
University overhead		-2 036	-2 036
Depreciation		-82	-187
Internal co-financing SND	2.	-807	0
Scholarships for transfer	4.	-112	0
Exchange loss		-3	0
Total		-22 828	-22 856
Activity expenses			
Staff Travel		-804	-823
Conference/course fees		-81	-73
SND Conferences		-290	-291
DoSp*/Consortium Activities	13.	-174	-169
Total		-1 349	-1 356
Total Expenses		-24 177	-24 212
RESULT		702	0
Opening balance 2018		6 001	
Ending balance 2018		6 702	

Personnel

SND Gothenburg

Administration and Services

Director
Max Petzold

Finance
Administrator
Ann Nordström

IT Coordinator
Birger Jerlehag

Senior Advisor
Iris Alfredsson

Legal Officer
Kristina Ullgren

Communications
Officer
Helena Rohdén

Communications
Officer
Matilda Lindmark

Project
Coordinator
Daniel Knezevic

Without picture:
Administrative Assistant, Anna Brami

Deputy Director,
Team Leader
Elisabeth Strandhagen

Research
Coordinator
Stefan Ekman

Administrative
Coordinator
Eira Brandby

Data Manager
Sofia Agnesten

Data Manager
Caspar Jordan

Data Manager
Jeremy Azzopardi

Data Manager
Martin Brandhagen

Data Manager
Dimitar Popovski

Data Manager
Ulf Jakobsson

Data Manager
Sara Svensson

Research
Coordinator
David Rayner

Data Manager
Malin Lundgren

Data Manager
Ilze Lace

Service
Coordinator
Rufus Latham

Without picture:
Language Coordinator, Lisa Isaksson

IT and Development

System Developer,
Team Leader
Johan Fihn Marberg

IT Architect
Olof Olsson

System Developer
Fabian Samuelsson

System Developer
Pablo Millet

System Developer
Stefan Jakobsson

Without picture:

System Developer, Alireza Davoudian System Developer, Joakim Larsson
IT Technician, Akira Olsbänning System Developer, Adriana Aires

Domain Specialists

Gustav Nilssonne
Karolinska Institutet

Anna Axmon
Lund University

Margaretha Hellström
Lund University

Darren Spruce
MAX IV,
Lund University

Anders Brändström
Umeå University

Christel Häggström
Umeå University

Karina Nilsson
Umeå University

Anders Moberg
Stockholm University

Ylva Toljander
Swedish University of
Agricultural Sciences

Without picture:

Fredrik Bolmsten, MAX IV, Lund University Xavier de Luna, Umeå University
Pontus Hennerdal, Stockholm University Ida Taberman, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences

As well as Elisabeth Strandhagen, Iris Alfredsson and Stefan Ekman, who act as Domain Specialists at Gothenburg University.

Steering Committee

The Swedish National Data Service is from 1 January 2018 a consortium led by the University of Gothenburg. Members of the consortium are also Karolinska Institutet, Lund University, Stockholm University, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Umeå University, and Uppsala University.

Members:

Göran Landberg (Chair)

Deputy Vice-Chancellor and Professor at Institute of Biomedicine, University of Gothenburg

Mikael Hjerm

Professor at Department of Sociology, Umeå University

Lars Burman

Chief Librarian, Uppsala University

Karin Grönvall

Chief Librarian, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences

Astri Muren

Deputy Vice-Chancellor and Professor at Department of Economics, Stockholm University

Cecilia M. Björkdahl

Project Leader at Grants Office, Karolinska Institutet

Monica Lassi

Expert at LUNARC, Centre for Scientific and Technical Computing, Lund University

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